

Citizen Journalism in Sri Lanka: Content Creators on Facebook

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Abstract – Social media has become more popular among online users nowadays. Facebook is the most popular social media platform among users in the world as well as in Sri Lanka. Moreover, Facebook users have become influential content creators. Therefore, there are challenges and opportunities in citizen journalism at the local and international levels. The main purpose of the study is to examine the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka. The specific objective is to identify the opportunities and challenges of citizen journalism. Uses and Gratifications theory was used to examine the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka. A qualitative approach was adopted to collect data using interview method and observation method. The qualitative data were thematically analyzed. The results showed that content creators play a vital role in creating, editing, sharing, commenting, distributing etc. on Facebook. Moreover, the content creators in Sri Lanka use Facebook for their socio- economic, cultural, political and educational needs in day-to-day life. In addition to that, there are opportunities and challenges of citizen journalism. Therefore, media and information literacy should be increased among the citizens in the country to avoid disinformation, misinformation, mal information, hate speech, cyber harassment, bullying etc. Moreover, the citizens should be educated to use social media efficiently and effectively. It is also important to introduce a code of ethics for journalism including citizen journalism by practicing self-regulation or co-regulation within a democratic framework.

Keywords: Social Media, Facebook, content creators, citizen journalism, Sri Lanka.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media is popular among users worldwide. Because anyone can participate in creating, editing and sharing the content of social media if the person has access to the internet. "Social media are defined as a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content" (Kaplan & Haenlein 2010: 61). This shows that social media has emerged due to the second generation of internet- web 2 that allows users to create, edit, share and comment on social media content. Therefore, due to the active participation of content creators, a new form of journalism has emerged in the field of journalism. "Citizen Journalism explores citizen participation in the news as an evolving disruptive practice in digital journalism. This volume moves beyond the debates over the mainstream news media attempts to control and contain citizen journalism to focus attention on a different direction: the peripheries of traditional journalism. Here, more independent forms of citizen journalism, enabled by social media, are creating their own forms of news" (Wall, 2019:2).

Facebook is the most popular social media at the local and international levels. As far as the Sri Lankan context is concerned, the Meta's advertising resources indicate that Facebook had 6.55 million users in Sri Lanka in early 2023. Madhubhashini (2022) notes that people cannot actively participate in creating content of the mainstream media like electronic and print media. Because media ownership has authority to make decisions on the content of mainstream media and the audience cannot actively provide feedback for these

mainstream media. On the other hand, Facebook is the most popular social media platform among users in Sri Lanka. Facebook can be effectively used for the socio-cultural, political, economic, and educational needs of the citizens in their day-to-day life. People only need internet connectivity to freely create the content of Facebook. However, social media platforms should ensure the Freedom of expression of the general public while having a regulatory and monitoring mechanism maintained by social media ownership. But still there can be negative and positive impacts of social media on users.

It is evident that citizens can actively participate in creating the content of social media, mainly the content of Facebook, but there are negative and positive impacts of Facebook. In this context, the main problem is what are the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka. The literature review also shows that no research has been conducted on citizen journalism and Facebook content creators in Sri Lanka. Therefore, the main purpose of the study is to examine the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka. The specific objective is to identify opportunities and challenges of citizen journalism. Therefore, Uses and Gratifications theory was used to examine the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Flew (2014) notes that web 2.0 is a term that has been used to identify developments in internet, software, web applications etc. The most associated social media with web 2.0 are Wikipedia, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter etc. Moreover, Participation, interactivity, collaborative learning, and social networking are mainly encouraged by the concept of web 2.0. Therefore, the main characteristics of social media are openness, peering, sharing and acting globally.

According to the literature, social media like Facebook encourages users to actively participate in creating content apart from just being a user or an audience. Social media platforms also facilitate users for social networking, collaborative learning and making interactivity with others. Therefore, due to the technological innovations and facilities of Facebook, content creators can openly and easily create, share, edit and provide feedback on social media content locally and globally. "User created content is a term used to refer to sites such as blogs, practices such as citizen journalism where users are empowered to become creators and distributors of digital content. With citizen journalism, independent content is generated, and produced by a non-professional individual or organization that is not paid staff" (Flew:2014: 34). This shows that ordinary social media users can generate and distribute social media content. In this context, everyone can become an online content creator or a distributor.

It is also important to identify the citizen journalism practices at the global level. Due to gatekeeping and agenda setting of the different mainstream media, the content cannot be created by ordinary people. But individuals or a group of people get together and start creating and distributing social media content. For instance, in South Korea, Oh Yeon-ho and three of his colleagues started an online news content in 2000 as the majority of people in South Korea are dissatisfied with traditional journalism on mainstream media (Moghanizadeh, 2013). In Sri Lanka also there are citizen journalists who maintain online news pages, Facebook pages, blogs, YouTube channels to report news and current affairs.

On the other hand, online content creators use social media for socio-political, cultural, economic, educational needs etc., Moreover, people use social media for seeking and creating information, education, entertainment, motivation etc. (Madhubhashini, 2022). Gunawardena (2020) notes that people in Sri Lanka use social media for news and information and gossip websites are also used by some people. It is further highlighted that people mainly use their mobile phone to go online. The Asian Network for Free Election (2023)

reports that the Thai election in 2023 shows that social media is so powerful in changing public opinion drastically. The supporters of the current president Pita Limjaroenrat effectively used social media platforms mainly Instagram, Facebook, TikTok etc. for the election campaign. So, Pita became the president of Thailand due to the huge election campaign done on social media. Moghanizadeh (2013) notes that, the Iranian Green Movement was reported online by the protesters mainly via Facebook. Therefore, people all over the world were able to get a clear understanding of the Iranian civil conflict due to the online reporting done by the citizen journalists.

Citizen journalism has recently become more popular specially for natural and manmade disaster reporting and health reporting. For example, citizen journalists created content about the disasters such as Haiti earthquake and the floods in China and Pakistan, Flooding in the South and East Germany (Flew, 2014). Moreover, during the covid 19 pandemic, people created contents related to the pandemic locally and globally. Madhubhashini (2022) notes that people started mostly using social media for the information purpose during the covid 19 pandemic compared to the mainstream media. Moreover, people used social media to get information related to covid, online selling and buying, educational purposes etc. during pandemic. But there were some challenges in citizen journalism, especially during the Covid 19 pandemic due to disinformation, hate speeches, ethical issues etc. Furthermore, the news stories were also created without respecting the privacy of individuals. Disinformation about some products and beliefs like Dammika Paniya were circulated on social media. Therefore, the general public/ citizens should be educated on digital and media literacy. Dr. Ranga Kalansooriya, the regional advisor for Asia with International Media Support emphasized that though citizens have freedom to express their ideas on social media, sometimes the social media ownership is not ready for collaborations in ensuring the ethical standards of social media.

This shows that there are some challenges connected to social media ownership when it comes to citizen journalism. On the other hand, cyber bullying, cyber cheating, cyber harassment etc. are also serious issues connected to citizen journalism. Hate speech is another issue in citizen journalism. Samaratunge and Hattotuwa (2014) note that hate speech can be defined as the content that attacks people based on their actual or perceived race, ethnicity, national origin, religion, sex, gender, sexual orientation, disability or disease. A considerable amount of social media hate speech in Sri Lanka was also reported and the islamophobia in Sri Lanka is also clearly shown on social media.

When it comes to Covid 19 pandemic, there were also some hate speeches against different beliefs, races etc. For example, Muslims refused to claim the bodies in protest over the government's policy of cremation during the pandemic, which is forbidden under Islamic law. Therefore, hate speeches on this practice were created on social media (Madhubhashini, 2022).

On the other hand, online content creators are threatened and harassed by the authorities. The British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) reported in 2022 that the citizen journalist Zhang Zhan was sentenced to four years in prison in 2020 for reporting about COVID-19 in China on social media. According to the Annual report on Media Freedom in Sri Lanka published by the Free Media Movement in 2022, journalists are getting threatened over criticisms posted on Facebook and it is a serious issue connected to the safety and security of journalists. There were several internet shutdowns reported during the year 2022 which limit the freedom of expression of citizen journalists. Madhubhashini (2022) notes that there is also a digital divide between information rich and information poor in terms of internet access in Sri Lanka due to lack of infrastructure facilities, affordability issues, less computer literacy etc. But this gap has been limited after the covid 19 pandemic, but still network issues, low data transmission speed etc. are occurring due to lack of infrastructure and affordability issues.

The literature shows that citizen journalists can play an active role in creating and distributing online content. Moreover, citizen journalists can use social media for socio- political, cultural, economic, educational purposes etc. But citizen journalists should play a responsible role in creating online content without violating journalism ethics.

However, this study only focuses on Facebook to examine the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka and to identify the opportunities and challenges of citizen journalism. Therefore, Uses and Gratifications theory is the main theoretical framework of the study which mainly explains how people use specific media for their own needs. Katz, Hass & Gurevitch (1973) note that Uses and Gratifications theory is mainly concerned with how audiences actively select a specific medium to satisfy the needs and gratifications. Therefore, people play an active role in media consumption.

As far as this study is concerned, citizens mainly choose Facebook among the other social media to create and distribute online content. Moreover, citizen journalists use social media to create content to satisfy their socio- economic, cultural, political and educational needs in day-to-day life. Therefore, Uses and Gratifications theory also mainly focuses on five main needs. Five needs that people bring to their media consumption in Uses and Gratification theory are cognitive needs (acquiring information, knowledge, and understanding), affective needs (emotional pleasurable or aesthetic experience), personal integrative needs (strengthening credibility, confidence, stability, and status), social integrative needs (strengthening contacts with family, friends, etc.) and tension release needs (escape and diversion)” (Katz, Hass, and Gurevitch 1973: 167). On the other hand, online content creators can experience the opportunities and challenges of citizen journalism. Therefore, the following theoretical framework/ model can be developed for this study based on the Uses and Gratifications theory.

Uses and Gratifications on Facebook

Fig -1: Proposed model for the study

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The objectives of the study are to examine the citizen journalism practices in Sri Lanka and to identify opportunities and challenges of citizen journalism. Therefore, the qualitative approach was adopted to collect data using the interview method and observation method. Gill et al. (2008) note that interviews provide a deeper understanding of a social phenomenon. In other words, detailed insights of a particular subject or an

area can be collected from individual participants using the interview method. Therefore, personal interviews were conducted with twenty-five content creators on Facebook. The purposive sampling was used to select these content creators. Moreover, samples were selected representing different age groups such as 15-30 age group, 31-40 age group, 41-50 age group, 51-60 age group and 61-70 age group and different user categories such as students, professionals, housewives, politicians, businessmen and online journalists. Five content creators were selected from each age group in Colombo district for interviews. Because Facebook is the most popular social media platform in Sri Lanka, and the Facebook users/ content creators are mainly reported in the Colombo District (Gunawardena, 2020).

In addition to the interviews, the observation method was used to collect data. Therefore, the Facebook pages maintained by these content creators were observed to examine the citizen journalism practices. The data collection was done with the support of five research assistants in the month of September 2023. The qualitative data were analyzed thematically. Some limitations were caused in the study due to some geographical and subjective reasons. The respondents were only selected from the Colombo district due to time and financial reasons. Subjectively, this study mainly focuses on Facebook. But the population, sample size and subject area can be expanded to find more practical findings in a future study in a systematic and methodical manner.

4. DISCUSSION

As far as the demographic details of the content creators are concerned, the findings showed that there were fourteen males and eleven females. Since the equal representation of age groups was taken, there was a limitation in taking age wise profiles in the study. But Gunawardena (2020) notes that the youngsters mainly use Facebook and male users have the highest Facebook usage compared to females in Sri Lanka.

When it comes to use of media, the findings showed that twelve out of twenty-five respondents- 48% used Facebook for the information, entertainment, motivation and education needs among mainstream media such as TV, radio and print media and among other social media platforms. This shows that a considerable number of respondents used Facebook compared to the other social media such as You Tube, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter etc. and mainstream media. Gunawardena (2020) also shows that people mainly use legacy media or mainstream media for their information needs compared to social media.

Uses and Gratifications theory, which is the main theory of the study, mainly explains how audiences actively select a specific medium to satisfy the needs and gratifications. Therefore, the findings showed that Facebook is more popular among the respondents compared to the other social media platforms. Because the content creators can easily connect with Facebook compared to other social media for sharing their experiences, feelings and emotions, gaining knowledge and entertainment, seeking information, interacting with others, releasing tension and isolation etc. This shows that people actively use Facebook to fulfill their needs as mentioned in the proposed model. Therefore, the findings showed that content creators mainly used Facebook to create content related to socio-economic, political, cultural, emotional, educational, moral etc. factors, situations, contexts and situations. In addition to creating Facebook content, content creators used Facebook for editing, sharing, distributing and commenting on online content.

A 42-year-old housewife said "I use Facebook in my leisure time. Though I am a housewife I am doing a small business. I prepare food and cake. So, I use a separate Facebook page to sell them and find customers. So, I add pictures of them and my contact details interactively to this page. I also follow some cooking and food related Facebook pages at the local and international levels to learn new recipes, techniques, food

decorations, deliveries etc. In addition to that, I use my own Facebook page to share pictures of my cooking, gardening, family occasions etc. I share poems written by me on this Facebook page. There are good and bad things on Facebook. So, a man sent me unnecessary messages on Messenger and shared pictures of mine which were edited adding the body part of an actress. So, I faced such bad experiences and I had to complain to the relevant authorities about this”.

This particular case shows that people use Facebook to fulfil affective needs such as entertainment, emotional pleasurable or aesthetic experience while fulfilling tension release needs. Cognitive needs such as acquiring, creating, distributing information are also satisfied by maintaining a separate page for selling food, following and interacting with other related food pages. Social integrative needs and personal integrative needs are also fulfilled by using Facebook. Because networking, peering, sharing, collaborative learning, confidence, stability, and status can also be done using Facebook. The results further showed that Facebook can be positively used for socio- economic, cultural and educational purposes according to the Uses and Gratifications theory. In other words, citizen journalism provides several opportunities for users to empower themselves socially, morally, culturally, economically, politically etc. On the other hand, the results showed that there were issues connected to Facebook such as cyber bullying, harassment, cheating etc. Moreover, creating fake photographs and videos and sharing them on social media, blackmailing etc. can be considered as challenges of citizen journalism. Galagedarage (2015) notes that social media like Facebook provide several opportunities for citizens to create, share, edit and interact with the content. But there are certain issues connected to Facebook such as disinformation, misinformation, mal information, hate speech, cyber bullying, harassment, cheating etc.

The results further showed that learners also used Facebook to fulfill their needs. Moreover, undergraduate and postgraduate students created separate Facebook pages and shared their notes, experiences, information etc. to successfully do their studies. But parents emphasized that the students should not become addicted to social media like Facebook due to phonography, cyber bullying, harassment, cheating etc.

A 52-year-old professional said that “I use social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, LinkedIn etc. for my personal and professional work. But I mostly use Facebook among them. But unfortunately, we face some issues in using Facebook. When compared to other mainstream media, everyone can create the content of social media. So, this is a great opportunity that we have as citizens in this global world. But on the other hand, I faced several issues in using Facebook. As I am Muslim, people used social media especially Facebook to attack me about some professional matters. The news of this incident went viral, and my family and I had to face a lot of problems. Several fake news stories were also circulated on this particular matter”.

As far as this particular incident is concerned, challenges and opportunities of citizen journalism can be clearly identified. Because social media including Facebook can be used for day to day needs as mentioned in the Uses and Gratification theory. Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights protects the Freedom of expression of every individual in the world. Article 14 of the Sri Lankan constitution also ensures the freedom of expression. Therefore, any citizen can create the content of social media including Facebook, apart from sharing, distributing, reacting and editing the content.

But on the other hand, the findings showed that Facebook was also negatively used to damage images of different individuals by sharing disinformation, misinformation, mal information, hate speech etc. Since everyone can create the content, it is difficult to manipulate the information. Because there are limited gate keepers and agenda setters on social media compared to the mainstream media. As far as the above-

mentioned case is concerned, the privacy of the individual professional and his family was violated apart from the circulating disinformation and hate speech. This also shows that ethics are violated in citizen journalism. A politician who maintains a Facebook page also mentioned that his image is badly destroyed on Facebook as there is no proper media regulatory mechanism in the country. "The spread of disinformation and hate speech on social media is a recurring issue of concern in the global digital space. Both hate speech and disinformation are often linked to one another. In 2018, a video allegedly containing footage of a Muslim restaurant owner in Ampara being confronted for serving food that contained 'sterilization pills' was widely circulated on social media. Over the next few days, disinformation and hate speech was propagated on social media platforms to create a false impression that there was a Muslim conspiracy to sterilize the Sinhala population, leading to violence in Ampara. In the following weeks, a separate incident triggered further anti-Muslim violence and riots in Digana. These riots were coordinated using social media platforms specially Facebook and resulted in widespread destruction of private property belonging to Muslims" (Report on Better moderation of hate speech on social media: A Sri Lankan case study for reputational-cost approaches, 2021:15). It is evident that citizen journalism ethics are not properly maintained by content creators on Facebook.

The Sri Lankan government also shut down Facebook several times due to various reasons. Moreover, the internet was shut down during the Digana incident to avoid hate speech etc. But Facebook was shut down during "ARAGALAYA" in Sri Lanka to violate freedom of expression (Madhubhashini, 2022). Report on Better moderation of hate speech on social media: A Sri Lankan case study for reputational-cost approaches (2021) also mentions Facebook community standards and its enforcement should protect the rights of Facebook users. Therefore, it is prohibited violent or dehumanizing speech, harmful stereotypes, statements of inferiority, expressions of contempt, disgust or dismissal, cursing, and calls for exclusion or segregation' in relation to protected characteristics of people such as race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, caste, gender, and sexual orientation, but there are no clear parameters of what constitutes disinformation and misinformation. Ranga Kalansooriya, the regional advisor for Asia with International Media Support emphasized that big data companies like Meta, You Tube, Google etc. are powerful in handling the information flow of the entire world. But some social media companies are only cooperative in protecting community rights and maintaining ethical practices.

The findings also showed that some content creators had become online journalists. Therefore, a 35-year-old online journalist said that "Previously I worked for a formal media institute as a journalist. But three years ago, I resigned and started a new journey as an online content creator/ journalist. Now I maintain a separate Facebook page, blog and you tube channel to report contemporary news. I have many followers and subscribers on these social media sites. The online users interact and engage in commenting, providing feedback, sharing the content etc. Most people interact with my online reporting on the Facebook page. I always try to adhere to journalism ethics. But some content creators violate ethical practices in creating content. Anyway now online journalists are also threatened for their reporting against the current government". It is evident that there are active content creators/ journalists on social media. Some respondents also emphasized that they used social media including Facebook for their affective needs, tension release needs, cognitive needs, social integrative needs and personal integrative needs as highlighted in the Uses and Gratification theory. Media Freedom in Sri Lanka: Annual Report 2022 published by Free Media Movement emphasized that content creators were arrested for their reporting on "ARAGALAYA" in 2022. For instance, Vimukthi Ranasinghe was called to the crime Division in Dematagoda and questioned about his social media activities and he was arrested by the Criminal Investigation Department at his home in Maharagama after a

few days. But on the other hand, ordinary people actively used social media including Facebook to make a strong public opinion on ARAGALAYA.

Therefore, the results showed that even though citizen journalism is a new trend on social media, still there are challenges in social media reporting. Another challenge is the digital divide. Madhubhashini (2021) also notes that the digital divide is a critical issue in terms of internet usage. The citizens in remote areas face network issues, technical issues and IT infrastructure issues compared to the people in the urban areas. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the policy makers to bridge the gap between information rich and poor. But the internet users have increased after the covid 19 pandemic. Therefore, social media users also gradually increased. The findings of this study also showed that digital divide is one of the challenges in citizen journalism.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings showed that Facebook is more popular among the respondents compared to the other social media platforms. Because the content creators can easily connect with Facebook compared to other platforms for sharing their experiences, feelings and emotions, gaining knowledge and entertainment, seeking information, interacting with others, releasing tension and isolation etc. This shows that content creators actively used Facebook to fulfill their needs as mentioned in the proposed model. Therefore, the findings showed that content creators mainly used Facebook to create content related to socio-economic, political, cultural, emotional, educational, moral etc. factors, situations, contexts and situations. In addition to creating Facebook content, content creators edit, share, distribute and comment on online content. In other words, people used social media including Facebook for their affective needs, tension release needs, cognitive needs, social integrative needs and personal integrative needs as highlighted in the Uses and Gratification theory. Moreover, the different professionals, students, businessmen, housewives etc. created content on Facebook to fulfil their needs.

In addition to the opportunities on Facebook, the findings showed that there were some challenges in citizen journalism such as disinformation, misinformation, mal information, hate speech, internet shutdowns, cyber bullying, harassments, cheating, challenges related to social media ownership, safety and security of citizen journalists and digital divide. Therefore, responsible parties should take necessary actions to overcome these issues to facilitate content creators on Facebook to fulfil their affective needs, tension release needs, cognitive needs, social integrative needs and personal integrative needs as highlighted in the Uses and Gratification theory.

Providing media and information literacy is the most important action that can be taken to empower citizen journalists in Sri Lanka. This helps citizen journalists to practice ethical reporting in content creation on social media including Facebook. Moreover, ethical reporting is important to avoid disinformation, misinformation, mal information, hate speech, cyber bullying, harassment, cheating etc. UNESCO also emphasized that "Media and information literacy empowers people to think critically about information and use of digital tools. It helps people make informed choices about how they participate in peace building, equality, freedom of expression, dialogue, access to information, and sustainable development" (UNESCO Annual Report, 2021:3). A code of ethics or guidelines should also be introduced to establish an ethical media culture while respecting the fundamental right to freedom of expression. Therefore, content creators on social media should also adhere to a code of ethics by practicing self-regulation or co-regulation within a democratic framework.

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